

THE WAYS OF TRANSLATING SOMATIC PHRASEOLOGISMS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10369197>

ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the concept of somatic phraseological expressions and their translation methods and types. In the process of translating, not only the culture and history of the translated language are analysed, but also translation by means of phraseological expressions in order to convey the original meaning to the listener from a pragmatic point of view. In such translated works, not losing the connotative colouring of the phrase shows that the translator used the right technique.

KEY WORDS

Somatic phraseological units, classification, group, world picture, national, concept, category, body, parts of body, genres of literature.

INTRODUCTION

When translating PhUs(phraseological units), special attention is also paid to translation methods. As we know, there are different translation methods. However, we tried to find answers to the questions, which of these methods is effective in translating PhUs, and which of them can show the essence and meaning of a phraseology in a completely different language. After the development of the science of translation theory, a number of scientific studies in the field of phraseology began to appear. This made it possible to compare specific aspects of phraseology, the essence of PhUs in different languages. Scholars who have conducted research in the field of phraseology have thoroughly interpreted their equivalents in different languages and translation methods. Let's analyze them and pay special attention to their translation methods when translating PhUs.

Ya.I.Retsker notes that phraseologies can be translated in two ways:

- a) by finding a suitable equivalent or analog of the phraseology;
- b) by way of description.[1,2]

B. N. Komissarov proposed the equivalent, analogical, calque, descriptive method and methods of replacing the corresponding text with phraseology in translation.[2,1]

P. K. Minyar-Beloruhev divided the translation of phraseology into five more methods:

- a) descriptive;
- b) concretization;
- c) generalization;
- d) antonyms;
- e) through translation, logical development of thought[3,1].

B. C. Vinogradov expresses the following opinion about the translation of phraseology: "The translator should try to translate phraseology by phraseology, sometimes it is impossible to apply this method, then it is possible to use the figurative method of translation, sometimes the method of calque"[4,1].

According to M. Ordudari, the best method of translation is the method of using "notes".[5.1] I.

K. Kobyakova, Y. A. Golikova, S. Vlahov, S. Florin and V. N. Komissarov(1990) investigated three types of FB translation methods[6.1]. They are as follows:

- a) phraseological equivalence;
- b) phraseological analogy;
- c) translate phrases using equivalent, non-analogous word combinations.

E.Y.Pishkova and I.F.Statova also suggest using five more types of translation methods when translating phraseological phrases:

- a) equivalence method;
- b) analog method;
- c) calaca method;
- d) the method of visual translation;
- e) method of translation of antonyms[7,1].

G'.T.Salomov distinguishes four principles of idiom translation:

- a) to look for the equivalent equivalent of the original phraseology in the target language;
- b) to find an equivalent alternative to the language into which the work is translated;
- c) to translate the phraseology exactly, word for word, i.e. on the basis of the kalka;
- d) by the method of visualization.

Focusing on the methods of translation, we will try to explain:

1. Equivalent translation - corresponding to the meaning and content of FB in both languages when converted from one language to another, e.g.: *tovuq miya* – *куриные мозги* – *bird brain/sparrow brain*.

2. Analogical translation is the same in meaning but completely or partially different in order, e.g.: *как воды в рот набрал* – *og'ziga tolqon solganday/og'zida qatiq ivitgandek* - *keep tum*. In a similar case, we can observe that one or two components of PhU are either semantically different.

3. Illustrated translation of the translation of the entire PhU with free combination, e.g.: *Ko'z-quloq bo'lib turmoq* – *быть настороже, начеку* – *to keep one's weather eye open*.

Figurative translation, that is, the translation of a fixed conjunction by a free conjunction. This case is used when there is no corresponding phrase in the target language, for example: *tili-tiliga kelishmoq* – *найти общий язык-see eye to eye*; *ko'zi o'tkir/uzoqni ko'radigan inson* – *дальновидный человек* – *Bird's eye view* va *worm's eye view* – *(like a bird that sees everything from above)*.

Translating antonyms means translating a negative meaning with a partitive form or a participial meaning with a negative form. The example of Uzbek language: *Bosh qorong'i ayol* – *в интресном положении* – *With child*.

In contrast to the English: *to keep one's head* – *o'zini yo'qotmaslik*, *to keep one's head above water* – *qarzga botmaslik* – *не вешать нос*, *to keep one's pecker up* – *ruhini cho'ktirmaslik*.

4. Calka. This method is used when it is necessary to emphasize the figurative content of a phraseology or when the phraseology cannot be translated by other methods.: *ko'zini ochmoq* – *открыть глаза* – *open one's eyes*.

5. Combined translation. After calquing, its meaning can be described by using the method of combined translation.: *O'zi yo'qning ko'zi yo'q* – *за спиной* – *when one's back is turned*; *og'zidagi luqmani yutolmaydi* – *шагу ступить не может* – *Couldn't organise a fart in a baked bean factory*.

PhUs are widely used in all genres of literature. A high-level translator does not ignore the meaning of a particular phrase in the process of translation. Without certain knowledge, it is impossible to evaluate the vividness and expressiveness of speech, it is difficult to understand jokes, puns, and sometimes the speech as a whole.

P. Faizullaeva and G. Makhmudov devoted their research to artistic translation and interpretation of national color from the point of view of translating phraseological combinations. They say that national coloring can create special difficulties in the translation process.

When translating PhUs, we paid special attention to the notion of their "cultural codes". It is known that the system of phraseological expressions of any language is characterized by its peculiarities. In particular, PhUs should have cultural, religious, historical, social and geographical expression. These aspects are reflected in the structure of PhUs, and each language is characterized by the appearance of its own differences. At the beginning of the chapter, when classifying PhUs, we paid attention to these aspects and proposed a separate classification. There are also some problems with the display of PhU "cultural codes" in the second language. In the following chapters of the research work, we conducted an analysis to show the "cultural codes" of PhU in each language and to show their difference in three languages with different systems. The analysis included the tasks of describing appropriate translation modes for expressing the "cultural codes" of PhU and clarifying their meaning through the semantic system of each language. Of course, through the cultural codes of somatic units, the linguocultural characteristics of the peoples were manifested in translation.

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